

**MODERN CONCEPT OF NATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING
METHODOLOGY: RESEARCH AND APPROACHES
(ON THE EXAMPLE OF ALIJON HAMROEV'S SCIENTIFIC SCHOOL)**

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Abstract This article discusses the modern concept of the methodology of teaching the native language, its theoretical foundations and practical application. The essence of the competency-based, communicative, person-oriented and integrative approaches formed on the basis of modern educational requirements is revealed. Also, the scientific and theoretical views, methodological proposals of the Alijon Hamroev scientific school, which played an important role in the development of the methodology of teaching the native language, and their significance in educational practice are analyzed.

Keywords: native language education, methodology, modern concept, competency-based approach, communicative approach, innovative education, Alijon Hamroev scientific school.

Introduction

The role and importance of the subject of the native language in the education system of independent Uzbekistan is incomparable. The native language is not only a means of communication, but also the main support of national thought, spirituality and culture. Therefore, improving the education of the native language in accordance with the requirements of the time, organizing it on the basis of scientifically based methodological concepts is considered one of the urgent tasks. Today, in the educational process, abandoning traditional approaches, modern methodological views that put the student in the center, encouraging him to independent thinking, communication and creativity, are gaining priority. It is in this process that a new concept of the methodology of teaching the native language is being formed. In the educational process, in addition to teaching students, using modern and effective innovative methods, as well as using various ICT tools in the lesson, students develop independent thinking, communicative

helps to form skills, approach science, research, and research among students, and effectively use knowledge. To achieve such a result, it is necessary to combine the use of innovative methods and modern information technologies in the teaching process. In this process, the teacher creates conditions for the development of the individual, the formation of education and upbringing, and at

the same time performs management and guidance functions. In the teaching process, the student becomes the main figure. Knowledge, experience, interactive methods of pedagogical technology and pedagogical skills provide students with qualified, advanced skills.

Theoretical foundations of the methodology of teaching the native language

The methodology of teaching the native language develops in close connection with the disciplines of pedagogy, psychology, linguistics and didactics. The modern methodological concept is based on the following theoretical foundations:

- the dialectical unity of language and speech;
- the psychological and intellectual development of the student's personality;
- the principle of acquiring knowledge through practical activity;
- the continuity of education and upbringing.

These foundations determine the content, form and methods of mother tongue education.

The subject of the methodology of teaching the mother tongue in primary grades performs the following tasks:

a) determine and justify the content, scope and current system of the mother tongue course in primary grades, that is, the program of the course (literacy, reading, grammar, spelling, speech development, etc.);

b) study the process of forming knowledge and skills in reading and writing, as well as the difficulties that students encounter in this process, analyze the causes of errors, and develop types of work that will help prevent and correct them;

d) develop methods and tools that will help students clearly understand and thoroughly master the educational material given in the mother tongue, apply the knowledge they have gained in practice, and contribute to the general development of students, that is, develop their intelligence, memory, observation, memorization, logical thinking, creative thinking, and speech;

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System of modern approaches

At the present stage, a number of modern approaches have been formed in the methodology of teaching the native language, which serve to increase the effectiveness of the educational process.

Competency approach

The competency approach in teaching the native language is aimed at the application of knowledge, skills and competencies in real-life situations. According to this approach, the student should not only memorize grammatical rules, but also be able to correctly and appropriately apply them in the speech process. As a result, linguistic, speech and communicative competencies are formed in students.

Communicative approach

The communicative approach is based on the study of language as a means of communication. In this approach, the lesson process is organized through dialogue, discussion, text analysis and creative tasks. The main goal is to develop students' oral and written speech.

Person-centered approach

This approach assumes consideration of the student's individual abilities, interests, and needs. In native language lessons, the student's personal activity is increased through differentiated tasks, independent work, and creative activities.

Integrative approach

The integrative approach requires teaching the native language in close connection with literature, history, culture, and other subjects. This broadens the students' worldview and develops interdisciplinary thinking.

Formation and development of the Alijon Hamroev scientific school

Alijon Hamroev is one of the prominent scientists who created a large scientific school in the field of native language teaching methodology. His scientific views are fully consistent with the modern concept of education. In the scientist's research, the issues of focusing native language teaching on speech activity, text-centered teaching, and increasing student activity occupy a leading place.

In native language teaching at the Hamroev scientific school:

- studying language units based on text;
- Methodological ideas such as:
- integration of speech activities;
 - use of interactive and innovative methods
- are put forward.

Methodological innovations within the scientific school

The methodological approaches developed by Alijon Hamroev are of great importance in the effective organization of native language lessons. According to him, the student should not be a passive listener, but an active participant in the lesson process. The lesson models proposed by the scientist serve to develop independent thinking and speech activity of students.

Also, textbooks, methodological recommendations and research works created within the scientific school are widely used in today's educational practice.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the modern concept of the methodology of teaching the mother tongue is aimed at improving the quality of education, developing the speech and communicative competence of students. The example of the Alijon Hamroev Scientific School shows that scientifically based and innovative approaches bring mother tongue education to a new level. In the future, it is important to further develop these scientific views and widely implement them in practice.

List of used literature:

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